

Practical Results for AOEEU

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Blue squares show the time required to compute isomorphism against the previous graph in the test set; Red diamonds show the time required to compute isomorphism against a shuffled version of the same graph.

All runtimes were measured on an unthrottled Intel Xeon E5620, and ran single-threaded. The system runs the Linux kernel, version 4.19, and did not run any other significant workload at the time of testing.

1. AOEEU/BFS-SHADOW

Figure 1.1. Affine Geometry

Figure 1.2. cfi-rigid-d3[2]

Figure 1.3. cfi-rigid-r2[2]

Figure 1.4. cfi-rigid-s2[2]

Figure 1.5. cfi-rigid-t2[2]

Figure 1.6. cfi-rigid-z2[2]

Figure 1.10. Hadamard matrix, with switched edges

Figure 1.7. cfi-rigid-z3[2]

Figure 1.11. Grids

Figure 1.8. Cai, Fürer, and Immerman

Figure 1.12. Grids, with switched edges

Figure 1.9. Hadamard matrix

Figure 1.13. Complete

Figure 1.14. Latin square

Figure 1.18. C-Miyazaki

Figure 1.15. Latin square, with switched edges

Figure 1.19. Complete-Miyazaki (k-mz)

Figure 1.16. Lattice

Figure 1.20. Augmented Miyazaki

Figure 1.17. Miyazaki

Figure 1.21. Augmented Miyazaki 2

Figure 1.22. Paley

Figure 1.26. Dawar Yeung, base[1]

Figure 1.23. Desarguesian projective planar

Figure 1.27. Dawar Yeung, mult[1]

Figure 1.24. Random, 1/10 edge probability

Figure 1.28. Steiner triple system

Figure 1.25. Random, 1/2 edge probability

Figure 1.29. Steiner triple system, with switched edges

Figure 1.30. Triangular

2. PRACTICAL RESULTS FOR AOE/DFS-SHADOW

Figure 2.1. Affine Geometry

Figure 2.2. cfi-rigid-d3[2]

Figure 2.3. cfi-rigid-r2[2]

Figure 2.4. cfi-rigid-s2[2]

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3. PRACTICAL RESULTS FOR AOE/HEURISTIC

Figure 3.1. Affine Geometry

Figure 3.2. cfi-rigid-d3[2]

Figure 3.3. cfi-rigid-r2[2]

Figure 3.4. cfi-rigid-s2[2]

Figure 3.5. cfi-rigid-t2[2]

Figure 3.6. cfi-rigid-z2[2]

Figure 3.7. cfi-rigid-z3[2]

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Figure 3.13. Complete

Figure 3.10. Grids, with switched edges

Figure 3.14. Latin square

Figure 3.11. Hadamard matrix

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References

- [1] A. Dawar and K. Khan. *Constructing Hard Examples for Graph Isomorphism*. 2018. arXiv: 1809.08154 [cs.CC]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1809.08154>.
- [2] D. Neuen and P. Schweitzer. “Benchmark Graphs for Practical Graph Isomorphism”. In: *25th European Symposium on Algorithms*. Ed. by K. Pruhs and C. Sohler. RWTH Publications, 2017. DOI: 10.4230/LIPIcs.ESA.2017.60. URL: <https://www.lics.rwth-aachen.de/go/id/rtok/>.